

A Study of Clinical Profile of Paraquat Poisoning and Predictors of Short Term Outcome in a Tertiary Care HospitalTanmoy Dutta¹, Amit De², Abhed Biswas³¹Senior Resident cum RMO, Dept. of General Medicine, North Bengal Medical College and Hospital, Darjeeling, West Bengal, India²Assistant Professor, Dept. of General Medicine, Tamralipto Government Medical College and Hospital, Tamluk, West Bengal, India³Assistant Professor, Dept. of General Medicine, North Bengal Medical College and Hospital, Darjeeling, West Bengal, India

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Abstract:

Background: Poisoning is a global public health problem. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that nearly 250,000 deaths occur globally due to poisoning each year, with pesticides alone causing 150,000 deaths. Most poisoning deaths occur in lower- and middle-income countries (LMIC). The number of deaths occurring from particular poisons or poison classes varies from place to place, and over time, as a result of changes in access, effective and timely medical management, preventative measures, and regulatory policies. Paraquat (1,1'-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridylum dichloride) is one of the most widely used herbicides.

Methodology: The study was conducted in the Department of General Medicine in collaboration with Department of Biochemistry, Radiology, ENT, Chest medicine, of Calcutta National Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata along with sonography unit of department of General medicine and Dialysis unit. 50 patients were recruited after taking written consent from the inpatient as well as outpatient department of Dept. of General Medicine of CNMCH.

Results: Mean age of female population was 38.14 ± 12.25 year which was slightly higher than mean age of male population (36.78 ± 11.85 year). Majority of male population belonged to the age group of (31 – 45) year. Predominantly people from farming background took PQ as a suicidal poison and majority of them were from a rural area. Study showed that majority of Paraquat poisoning was suicidal. Only 1 subject is exposed to it accidentally. Overall, suicidal poisoning is much more severe than accidental poisoning due to the consumption of higher doses of poison. Most common sign of paraquat poisoning was oral ulceration (94%) followed by tachypnoea (48%), icterus (32%) and Shock (14%). The present study showed that almost all patient had raised creatinine value during hospital stay. The most common cause of death was multi organ damage followed by Respiratory failure, shock, and renal failure (61%, 30%, 6% and 3% respectively).

Conclusion: PQ was used for suicide in rural area mainly from families dependent on cultivation. As a corrosive poison almost all patient with significant intake had local ulceration in mouth and pharynx. Its systemic toxicity can affect all major organs though kidney, lung and livers were commonly effected ones. By using consensus based guidelines we found that one third of the patient survived which was better than the data reported in last decade. Amount of ingestion was one of the main predictors of outcome whereas early hospital admission and early hemodialysis significantly increases the chance of survival.

Keywords: PQ, Poisoning, Clinical Profile, Prevalence, Outcome.

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Introduction

Poisoning is a global public health problem. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that nearly 250,000 deaths occur globally due to poisoning each year, with pesticides alone causing 150,000 deaths [1]. Most poisoning deaths occur in lower- and middle-income countries (LMIC) [2]. The number of deaths occurring from particular poisons or poison classes varies from place to

place, and over time, as a result of changes in access, effective and timely medical management, preventative measures, and regulatory policies. Pesticide poisoning has been a major problem in India since at least 1958, when 100 people died after consuming flour contaminated with the organophosphorus (OP) insecticide parathion. An estimated 230,000 suicides occur each year in

India, of whom at least 70,000 (30%) die from pesticide suicide [3,4,5]. Among them OP insecticides, aluminium phosphide, Organo chlorine, carbamate and pyrethroid insecticides, the herbicide paraquat, rodenticides, and fungicides were major pesticide classes that were identified as causing deaths. Paraquat (1,1'-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridylium dichloride) is one of the most widely used herbicides, First synthesized in 1882 but the herbicidal properties were not recognized until 1955 in the Imperial Chemical Industries (ICI) laboratories at Jealott's Hill. Paraquat was first manufactured and sold by ICI now Syngenta in early 1962 under the trade name Gramoxone. It held the largest share of the global herbicide market until recently overtaken by glyphosate [6,7,8]. It is a quick acting, nonselective herbicide, which destroys green plant tissue on contact and by translocation within the plant.

However, this product is highly toxic for humans and most animals. Its ingestion (often for suicide) can cause multiple organ failure, including liver insufficiency and lung fibrosis that can be life-threatening because of respiratory failure [9,10]. The first case of paraquat mortality was published in the British Medical Journal in 1966 [11]. At present paraquat is responsible for just 1.8% of all reported pesticide deaths in India. However, there was an increasing trend in paraquat poisoning in. A hospital based study performed during 1999–2006 reported five patients (three deaths) in Punjab, while a second from Tamilnadu reported ten patients with 100% mortality. A recent newspaper report states that paraquat poisoning is a problem in Orissa with more than 100 deaths reported during 2018 and 2019 [12,13,14]. If paraquat becomes widely used for agriculture and self-harm in India, there is the risk of a massive increase in deaths as occurred in China before its ban in 2016. Paraquat dichloride (24% sl) is the only formulation registered in India with Central Insecticide Board And Registration Committee. It is mainly used as herbicide for 9 crops. Paraquat dimethyl sulfate banned in India since 1993. Kerala govt. banned all type of paraquat in 2011 [15].

After a person ingests a large amount of paraquat, he or she is immediately likely to have pain, swelling and ulcer of the mouth and throat. The next signs of illness following ingestion are gastrointestinal such as nausea (53.7%); vomiting (43.9%); epigastric pain (36.6%); mucosal lesions of oral cavity and pharynx (85.4%). Severe gastrointestinal symptoms may result in dehydration, electrolyte abnormalities, hematemesis, peptic perforation and low blood pressure [16]. In general, ingestion of large amounts of paraquat leads to the following signs/symptoms within a few days to a few days: Kidney is the main route of excretion as well as one

of the most affected organ .Significant increases in serum creatinine (Cr) was seen in 61% of patients. The mean \pm SD of Cr for these patients was 3.9 ± 2.1 mg/dl (Min=1.6, Max=8.8)[17]. Almost all patient with significant amount of paraquat poisoning have acute kidney injury. It may range from asymptomatic to oliguria, anuria with uremic signs and symptoms. Hepatic involvement associated with a bad prognosis in this poisoning. Acute hepatitis was seen in 31.7% of patients. Increased serum bilirubin was seen in 22% of patients. Time of involvement and severity of injury depends on amount of consumption. It mostly occur as a part of multi organ dysfunction. Isolated liver involvement though rare but reported in literature. Lung is a major target organ involved in paraquat poisoning. Though lung is affected in later part of poisoning, it is one of the most common cause of mortality and long term morbidity. Manifestation can be range from chemical pneumonitis, pulmonary oedema to respiratory failure.

Respiratory failure were clinically observed in 39% .In rare cases it may results in spontaneous pneumothorax known as Daisley Barton Syndrome [18]. Though central nervous system generally spared from toxic effects of paraquat, but in certain cases it may result in confusion, seizures, and coma. Several studies link long-term paraquat exposure to developing Parkinson's disease. These studies propose that paraquat increases Parkinson's disease risk by creating oxidative stress that damages and kills neurons that produce dopamine [19].

Altered mental status in paraquat poisoning carries bad prognosis but it is not clear whether it is due to toxic effect of poison or as a result of multi organ dysfunction. It directly affects the cardiac myocytes and hampers it contractility results in shock. Sometime hypovolemic shock and neurogenic shock also complicates the scenario. Because of multisystem involvement paraquat is considered to be a very lethal poison. Mortality rate of acute paraquat poisoning lies between (50 – 90) %. So, it is now banned in 32 countries. In spite of being such a lethal poison there are only few studies to describe the characteristics and outcome variable of this poison .So , in a tertiary care hospital of Kolkata a study is carried out to find out the clinical profile of paraquat poisoning and predictors of short term outcome.

Objectives:

1. To find out the prevalence of acute paraquat poisoning
2. To find out the clinical profile of acute paraquat poisoning patients
3. To find out the variables which determine the outcome of acute paraquat poisoning

Material and Methods

This Institution based descriptive observational study was conducted among the 50 indoor patients admitted at Department of General Medicine, Calcutta National Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata and and Dialysis unit for the period of 18 months (From 1st January, 2021 to 30th June, 2022).

Inclusion Criteria:

- All patients with history of paraquat ingestion within last 10 days.
- Patients who give written consent to participate in the study
- Exclusion Criteria:
- Patient with history of another poison ingestion with paraquat
- Patients who took paraquat only in mouth but not ingested.
- Patients who are suffering from any comorbidities like chronic heart failure, chronic liver disease, chronic kidney disease.

Data were collected by study proforma consisting history, clinical examination with special emphasis on abdominal, heart and chest examination,

appropriate investigation. Statistical Analysis was done using IBM SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) Version 26.

The mean and standard deviation, percentages and ratio were calculated and are presented in the form of tables. The two groups were compared with other variables.

For statistical significance value, chi-square test and test of proportion was applied. Multi variate analysis of variables with significant correlation was carried out using stepwise logistic regression analysis.

Discriminant analysis was used for developing combined predictability of variables. A statistical significance of $p < 0.05$ were considered.

Observation and results:

Mean age of female population was 38.14 ± 12.25 year which was slightly higher than mean age of male population (36.78 ± 11.85 year). Majority of male population belonged to the age group of (31 – 45) year. More than one third of the female population was less than 30 years age group and majority (71.42) % was less than 45 years age group.

Table 1: Distribution of study population according to age group and sex

Age	Male	Female
≤ 30 year	9 (25 %)	5 (35.71 %)
(31 - 45) year	18 (50 %)	5 (35.71 %)
(46 - 60) Year	8 (22.22 %)	4 (28.58 %)
> 60 year	1(2.78%)	0 (0 %)

Table 2. Interval between Ingestion and Hospital Admission (Hour)

Interval between Ingestion And Hospital Admission (Hour)	Number	Percent
< 12 hour	13	26
12 hour - 24 hour	23	46
25 hour - 48 hour	7	14
> 48 hour	7	14

Most of the patients 94% admitted within (12 – 24) hour of ingestion. Nearly one fourth of the patient got early standard treatment (< 12 hour).

Table 3: Duration of hospital stay and amount of ingestion

	Maximum	Minimum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Mean Duration Of Hospital Stay (Day)	27	2	11.26	6.21
Mean Amount Of Ingestion (ml)	250	20	116.6	55.99

Mean duration of hospital stay of study population was 11.26 day with a standard deviation of 6.21 day. Mean and standard deviation of amount of ingestion was 116.6 ml and 55.99 ml respectively.

Table 4: Clinical Parameter on Admission

Clinical Parameter	Present	Absent	Percentage
Oral Ulceration	47	3	94
Tachypnea	24	26	48
Icterus	16	34	32
Neurological Involvement	13	37	26
Oliguria	8	42	16
Shock	7	43	14
GI Bleed	6	44	12

Most common sign of paraquat poisoning was oral ulceration followed by tachypnea and icterus. GI bleed was the least common presentation of paraquat poisoning among the study population.

Table 5: Laboratory and imaging Parameter

	Present	Absent	Percentage
Anemia	18	32	36
Thrombocytopenia	6	44	12
Leucocytosis On Admission	1	49	2
Raised Creatinine	46	4	92
Raised Bilirubin	22	28	44
CXR suggestive of lung involvement	21	29	42

Study shows almost all patient have a raised creatinine value during hospital stay. Almost no patient shows signs of sepsis (leucocytosis) on day of admission. Around 40 % population shows laboratorial or radiological evidence of liver and lung involvement.

Figure 1: Cause of death

Most common cause of death was multi organ damage. One third of the study population died due to Respiratory complications.

Figure 2: Comparison interval between ingestion to hospital admission and outcome

Mortality increases with delay in hospital admission. All patient died who admitted beyond 24 hour of ingestion which is statistically significant (P value 0.0231).

Figure 3: Comparison of bilirubin level and creatinine level between deceased and survived population

Paradoxically mean serum creatinine level was higher in survived group than in deceased group (5.12 and 4.48 respectively). On the other hand serum bilirubin was higher in deceased group though it was not statistically significant (p – value - 0.063).

Figure 4: Comparison of radiological abnormality in chest x – ray with outcome

Mortality rate among patient with abnormal chest x – ray was 90.5 %. It was statistically higher than the other group (p – value - 0.018628).

Table 6: Distribution of outcome

	Frequency	Percent
Death	33	66.0
Discharge	17	34.0
Total	50	100.0

One third of the patient survived and discharged to follow up with standard treatment.

Table 7: Comparison of presence of anemia and thrombocytopenia with outcome

	Anemia (Hemoglobin : <12 – Female <13 – Male)			Thrombocytopenia (Platelet Count <150000)		
	Present	Absent		Present	Absent	
Discharge	3	14	0.052317	1	16	0.339354
Death	15	18		5	28	

There was no statistically significant impact of anemia and thrombocytopenia on outcome (p – value - 0.052317 and 0.339354 respectively).

Table 8: Comparison of presence of leucocytosis on admission and later part of hospital stay with outcome

Time	Count / mm ³	Outcome		p – value
		Death	Recovered	
Total Leucocyte Count on or before Day 5	<12000	12	10	0.129621
	>12000	21	7	
Total Leucocyte Count beyond Day 5	<12000	4	8	0.028265
	>12000	10	3	

Leucocytosis in early part of hospital stay was not a significant indicator of outcome (p – value - 0.129621). Although increased total leucocyte count in the later part of hospital stay carried statistically significant higher chance of mortality.

Table 9: Comparison of bilirubin level and creatinine level between deceased and survived population

	Outcome	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	p-value
Mean Creatinine Value	D	33	4.48	1.88	0.329
	R	17	5.12	2.65	
Mean Bilirubin Value	D	33	2.23	1.85	0.063
	R	17	1.32	0.83	

Paradoxically mean serum creatinine level was higher in survived group than in deceased group (5.12 and 4.48 respectively). On the other hand serum bilirubin was higher in deceased group though it was not statistically significant (p – value - 0.063).

Discussion

The study population showed male predominance. Greater than two third of patients (72 %) were male which was similar to the findings described by and Raghavendra Rao et al. And R Ravichandran et al. Where male population was 65.4 % and 65 % respectively [20,21]. Majority of male population belonged to the age group of (31 – 45) year. More than one third of the female population was less than 30 years age group and majority (71.42) % was less than 45 years age group. This is similar to study done by Deepak Amalnath et al. where majority of population was less than 40 years of age in both gender [21].

The study showed that majority of Paraquat poisoning was suicidal. Only 1 subject is exposed to it accidentally. Delirrad et al.[22] reported that 89.7% of patients with poisoning were suicide related; the corresponding suicide figures in Amiri et al.[23] and Sabzghabae et al.[24] studies were 76.9% and 100%, respectively. Overall, suicidal poisoning is much more severe than accidental poisoning due to the consumption of higher doses of poison. Mean duration of hospital stay of the study population was 11.26 day with a standard deviation of 6.21 day which is higher than what was found by Mohammad Majidi et al.[17] (5.75±4.6 days). They also found that the mean ± SD of ingested paraquat was 149.3±225.4 ml which in the present study was 116.6 ml ± 55.99 ml. Most common sign of paraquat poisoning was oral ulceration (94%) followed by tachypnoea (48%), icterus (32%) and Shock (14%). GI bleed was the

least common presentation of paraquat poisoning among the study population. In concordance with it BH Srinivas et al.[21] in a Retrospective Study of 55 Patients From a Tertiary Care Center in Southern India described that all patient with poisoning had oral or pharyngeal ulcer. Lung injury was documented in 61.8%. Hypotension was documented in 32.7%.

The present study showed that almost all patient had raised creatinine value during hospital stay. Almost no patient shows signs of sepsis (leucocytosis) on day of admission. Around 40 % population showed laboratorial or radiological evidence of liver and lung involvement. R Ravichandran et al. [21] similarly found acute kidney injury in 81.8%, increased bilirubin (> 2 mg/dL) in 33.3%, lung infiltrate in 28.57%. The most common cause of death was multi organ damage followed by Respiratory failure, shock, and renal failure (61%, 30%, 6% and 3% respectively). No Patient died of isolated liver injury or CNS dysfunction. Similar findings were observed by Mohammad Delirrad et al.[22] The most common causes of death were multi-organ failure in (57.9%) followed by respiratory failure (31.6%), cardiogenic shock (2.4%) and hemorrhage (2.4%). Though hospital stay was more in survived group (mean - 12.94 ± 7.08 day) than deceased group (mean - 10.39 ± 5.73) but that was statistically non-significant (p-value - 0.176). Similar value was observed in Mohammad Delirrad [22] study (mean in survived - 7.25±4.35 , in deceased - 4.01 ± 4.43, p – value - 0.024) . Whereas amount of ingestion among deceased (Mean ± SD = 143.03 ± 49.97) was significantly higher than survived population (Mean ± SD = 65.29 ± 23.75). Unpaired T – test show a p – value of 2.105 x 10⁻⁷. This findings also collaborate with the above study where amount of ingested paraquat (mL) in survived (23.4 ± 22.3) was significantly low than the deceased

group (290 ± 266) (p – value - 0.001). Dinis-Oliveira RJ, Duarte JA revealed similar result [25]. Mortality rate of patient with altered consciousness on admission was 92.3 %. It was significantly higher than patients with normal consciousness level (p – value - 0.019928). In a similar type of study statistical significance of CNS involvement with outcome was established by Amiri AH et al. (p – value - 0.038)[23]. 83 % of patient admitted with respiratory distress died which was significantly higher than the population without distress where the mortality rate was 42 % (p – value - 0.000232).

Chance of survival was significantly higher in patients admitted without shock (p – value - 0.040589). The study showed that presence of shock on admission in PQ poisoning was associated with 100 % mortality. Among patients admitted without oral ulcer mortality was nil. GI bleed in patients with PQ poisoning carries a grave prognosis. In this study all patient with GI bleed died. As PQ have corrosive property, absence of oral ulcer signify very low amount intake. On the other hand GI bleed associated with large amount of consumption what is necessary to cause gastric ulcer and erosion. There is no statistically significant impact of anemia and thrombocytopenia on outcome (p – value -0.052317 and 0.339354 respectively). Leukocytosis in early part of hospital stay was not a significant indicator of outcome. Although increased total leucocyte count in the later part of hospital stay carried statistically significant higher chance of mortality. On the other hand serum bilirubin was higher in deceased group though it was not statistically significant (p – value - 0.063). Mortality rate among patient with abnormal chest x – ray was 90.5 %. It was statistically higher than the other group (p – value - 0.018628). Goudarzi F et al.[26] found that only 35% patient with respiratory failure shows radiological abnormality which was much lower than this study. But at the same time he found it to be significantly associated with negative outcome [110]. Survival decreases with delay in initiation of dialysis. Though it was not statistically significant (p – Value - 0.0934).

Conclusion

Our study conclude that although overall study population had male predominance, young females had a higher tendency of suicide attempt. PQ was used for suicide in rural area mainly from families dependent on cultivation. As a corrosive poison almost all patient with significant intake had local ulceration in mouth and pharynx. Its systemic toxicity can affect all major organs though kidney, lung and livers were commonly effected ones. By using consensus based guidelines we found that one third of the patient survived which was better than the data reported in last decade. Most common

cause of death was multi organ damage .One third of the study population died due to Respiratory complications. Amount of ingestion was one of the main predictors of outcome whereas early hospital admission and early hemodialysis significantly increases the chance of survival. Manifestations of systemic toxicity like altered consciousness, shock, tachypnoea or severe local erosion that could be presented with GI bleed on admission was significantly associated with negative outcome. Hepatitis in early part of hospital stay and leucocytosis in later part carries grave prognosis whereas elevation of creatinine does not had any predictive value. However further multicentric studies with high number of patient population need to be initiated.

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